

LATIN AND ITS INFLUENCE ON MEDICINE

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Abstract. the paper examines the significance of Latin in contemporary medicine. As the principal language of the Catholic faith, Latin is utilized in the medical field to create terms related to anatomy, clinical practices, and pharmacology. Latin's contribution to the development of Western European languages and its influence on the Russian language through the introduction of loanwords, idiomatic expressions, and specialized terminology is substantial.

Latin in medicine is traditionally used in anatomical, clinical and pharmaceutical terminology. Knowledge of Latin allows doctors from different countries of the world to easily understand each other. The long tradition of using the Latin language in medicine serves as a unifying factor for physicians around the world and for the unification of medical education. More recently, most medical writings were written in Latin [2]. The great Russian surgeon N.I. Pirogov wrote in Latin, and I.P. Pavlov wrote an expressive message to the youth "Ad juventutem epistola" [3]. And even today, scientific works of this kind continue to be published. For the past three years, the journal Novus Hermes has been published at the Department of Classical Philology of Moscow State University, which publishes articles by famous classical philologists from all over the world.

The Latin language uses concise and aphoristic formulations that reflect or summarize experience in various fields of activity. The very concept of "winged words" is attributed to Homer, and as a term of literary criticism, it has been used since the 2nd half of the 19th century. The Latin language is very rich in such expressions due to its long and meaningful history.

Winged expressions arise in different ways and refer to different areas of human experience. The main subject areas or areas of classification are: aphorisms of worldly wisdom (proverbs, sayings, etc.), expressions from the field of scientific knowledge (medicine, jurisprudence, etc.), from literary works, as well as statements of famous historical figures who are obliged by its appearance in a particular situation. All these types of winged expressions are fully present in the history of the Latin language.

Therefore, it becomes evident that pursuing Latin language studies and ensuring a high proficiency in this field represent a crucial and timely objective for contemporary education.

References:

1. Хидояттов, Б.А. Микроциркуляторное русло кишечника и поджелудочной железы и его особенности при экспериментальном сахарном диабете / Б. А. Хидояттов, А. Т. Ахмедов // Морфология. – 2008. – Т. 133. – № 2. – С. 145-146. – EDN JUTXTT.7. Otto CM, Pearlman AS Textbook of clinical echocardiography. Philadelphia: WB Saunders Co.; 1995:418.
2. A.T.Akhmedov Kh.M.Aberaev Influence of coronavirus infection covid-19 to a echocardiographic changes in patients with a surveyof pneumonia // Академические

исследования в современной науке. – 2023. - Том 2 № 20. – стр. 57-59

3. AKHMEDOV , A. (2023). FUNCTIONING OF IMMUNE SYSTEM OF BABIES WITH CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS. Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук, 3(6 Part 2), 103–110.
4. Akhmedov, A., & Aberaev , K. (2023). INFLUENCE OF CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS IN A FUNCTIONING OF IMMUNE SYSTEM OF BABIES. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3(8), 15–21.
5. Akhmedov, A. T. . (2023). IMPACT OF CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS ON THE IMMUNE SYSTEM FUNCTION IN INFANTS. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 3(12), 191–199. Retrieved from <https://inovatus.es/index.php/ejmmp/article/view/2232>
6. Ahmedov, A. T. . (2023). CARDIAC ULTRASOUND ALTERATIONS IN INDIVIDUALS WITH PNEUMONIA RELATED TO COVID-19 INFECTION. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 3(12), 208–216. Retrieved from <https://inovatus.es/index.php/ejmmp/article/view/2234>
7. Akhmedov, A. T. . (2023). FACTORS INDICATING THE RISK OF CARDIOVASCULAR EVENTS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE POST CORONARY ARTERY BYPASS GRAFTING. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 3(12), 217–227. Retrieved from <https://inovatus.es/index.php/ejmmp/article/view/2235>
8. A. T., A. . (2023). COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF IMMUNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS IN LABORATORY ANIMALS WITH THYMUS AUTOIMPLANTATION OVER TIME. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 3(12), 200–207. Retrieved from <https://inovatus.es/index.php/ejmmp/article/view/2233>
9. Akhmedov A. T. (2023). Comparative Analysis of Immunological Measures in Lab Animals With Thymus Autoimplantation Over Time. AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI, 2(12), 1042–1048. Retrieved from <https://sciencebox.uz/index.php/amaltibbiyot/article/view/9226>
10. A. T. Akhmedov. (2023). Impact of Cytokines on the Onset and Progression of Arterial Hypertension. AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI, 2(12), 970–978. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/amaltibbiyot/article/view/9197>